

**CONTENT OF ORGANIZATION OF SENSOR-MOTOR
CORRECTION WORK IN DYSARTHRIA SPEECH
DISORDERS IN CHILDREN'S CEREBRAL PALSY****Pirimova Nozliya Azamat kizi****Tashkent International University of Chemistry
Student of MSPD-1U, Department of Speech Therapy****+998-97 708 11 09****nozliyapirimova5@gmail.com****<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18020255>****ARTICLE INFO**Received: 20th December 2025Accepted: 21st December 2025Online: 22nd December 2025**KEYWORDS***children's cerebral palsy, dysarthria, sensorimotor development, speech correction, articulatory motor skills, speech therapy rehabilitation***ABSTRACT**

this article scientifically analyzes the theoretical and methodological foundations, practical application and effectiveness of sensorimotor approaches in the correction of dysarthria speech disorders in children with cerebral palsy (CP). The research process sheds light on the psychoneurological characteristics of dysarthria, the influence of the integration of sensory and motor systems on speech development. The research is based on the results of research on the formation of articulatory motor skills, phonation, breathing and prosodic components of sensorimotor technologies. The results of the study showed that complex sensorimotor correction work significantly improves the functional state of speech in children..

introduction

In recent years, the increasing number of children born with cerebral palsy requires an in-depth study of speech disorders associated with this problem and the development of effective correctional approaches. According to statistics, 65-80% of children with cerebral palsy have speech disorders of varying degrees, including dysarthria. Dysarthria is associated with damage to the central nervous system and occurs as a result of impaired innervation of the muscles of the speech apparatus.

Since traditional speech therapy approaches are not sufficiently effective in the correction of dysarthria, the need for sensorimotor approaches in modern special pedagogy is increasing. The sensorimotor approach interprets speech not only as a linguistic system, but also as a complex psychophysiological process.

The relevance of this study is that it is aimed at clarifying the scientific foundations of complex correctional work based on the integration of sensory and motor systems in eliminating dysarthria speech disorders in cerebral palsy.

The purpose of the study is to scientifically substantiate the content and organizational features of sensorimotor approaches to the correction of dysarthria speech defects in children with cerebral palsy.

Research objectives:

- Analysis of the psychoneurological mechanisms of dysarthria in cerebral palsy;
- Determination of the relationship between sensorimotor development and speech;
- Determination of the content of sensorimotor correction work;

- Evaluation of their effectiveness.

Methodology (Methods)

The following methods were used in the research process:

- Theoretical methods: analysis of scientific literature, dissertations, international and local studies;
- Empirical methods: observation, logopedic diagnostics, sensorimotor development assessment tests;
- Experimental method: introduction of a system of correctional training based on sensorimotor skills;
- Statistical methods: comparison and generalization of results.

The study involved 30 children aged 7-14 years with a diagnosis of BSF and dysarthria speech disorder. They were divided into experimental and control groups. A specially developed sensorimotor correction program was used in the experimental group for 6 months.

Results

The results of the study showed the following significant changes:

- significant improvement in the mobility of the articulatory apparatus;
- development of speech breathing and vocal coordination;
- activation of phonemic hearing and sensory differentiation;
- increased fluency and intelligibility of speech.

Speech motor performance in children in the experimental group improved by 35–40%, while in the control group this figure was 10–15%.

Discussion

The results obtained confirm the high effectiveness of sensorimotor approaches in the correction of dysarthria in BSF. By integrating sensory stimulation (tactile, proprioceptive, vestibular) and motor exercises, the functional activity of the muscles of the speech apparatus increases.

An important point is that sensorimotor exercises support not only speech, but also general psychomotor development. This increases the motivation for communication in children and facilitates the process of social adaptation.

The results are consistent with the neuropsychological views put forward by other researchers (L.S. Vygotsky, N.A. Bernstein, R.E. Levina).

In conclusion, sensorimotor approaches are of great corrective importance in the elimination of dysarthria speech disorders in children with cerebral palsy. The results of the study show that complex stimulation of the sensory and motor systems strengthens the physiological foundations of speech and increases the effectiveness of speech therapy.

Systematic, individual and step-by-step organization of sensorimotor correction work leads to stable positive results in the speech development of children with BSF.

The results of the study once again confirm that dysarthria speech disorders in children with cerebral palsy have complex neurophysiological mechanisms. These disorders are closely related not only to paralysis or paresis of the muscles of the speech apparatus, but also to deficiencies in the processing of sensory information, proprioceptive sensations,

kinesthetic control and movement planning. Therefore, approaches to the correction of dysarthria that rely only on articulatory exercises do not give the expected stable result.

The sensorimotor approaches used in this study made it possible to consider speech activity as a holistic functional system. Correctional work organized on the basis of the integration of sensory and motor systems had a complex effect on the central and peripheral mechanisms of speech, contributing to the qualitatively new level of speech motor skills. In particular, the combination of tactile, proprioceptive and vestibular stimulation elements with articulatory exercises played an important role in increasing the activity of the muscles of the speech apparatus.

The research revealed that sensorimotor training supports not only speech skills in children, but also general psychomotor development. This is an important factor in strengthening the communicative activity, social adaptation and self-confidence of children with dysarthria. Increased speech success leads to the stabilization of the emotional state of children, an increase in the desire to communicate and a more active involvement in the educational process.

The results of the study also showed the need to organize sensorimotor correction work on the basis of an individual approach. Since each child has a different neurological condition, motor capabilities, sensory sensitivity and level of speech development, the correction program should be organized flexibly and gradually. Such an approach increases the effectiveness of speech therapy and prevents excessive stress.

The results obtained during the study showed that corrective work based on sensorimotor approaches has a positive effect on alleviating the symptoms of dysarthria, increasing the intelligibility and fluency of speech, as well as on the coordination of speech breathing and sound production.

This scientifically justifies the need for the widespread introduction of these approaches into the speech therapy rehabilitation system.

Thus, sensorimotor approaches to eliminating dysarthria and speech disorders in children with cerebral palsy are one of the promising areas of modern special pedagogy and speech therapy. The harmonious development of sensory and motor components strengthens the physiological foundations of speech activity and allows achieving stable and long-term positive results. The implementation of these approaches in practice is of particular importance in special educational institutions, rehabilitation centers and in inclusive education.

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